

COMPETENCY NEEDS OF SPECIAL EDUCATION LECTURERS IN UTILIZATION OF E-LEARNING PLATFORMS FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SERVICE IN FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, PANKSHIN

By

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Abstract

This study assessed the competencies required by special education lecturers in Federal College of Education, Pankshin for effective utilization of e-learning platforms for inclusive education service delivery. The study had three objectives, research questions, and a hypothesis. The design for the study was descriptive survey with the population of 15 special education lecturers in the Department of Special Education, FCE, Pankshin. Data collection employed validated questionnaires with a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.82. The data for the study was collected using a direct approach facilitated by the three researchers. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation were applied to address the research questions, while t-Tests, supported by the Statistical Package for Social Science at a 0.05 significance level was used to test the hypothesis. The findings revealed that special education lecturers in Federal College of Education, Pankshin, have varying levels of competencies in utilizing e-learning platforms, with strengths in creating interactive online courses and understanding e-learning platforms, but weaknesses in designing cooperative online learning activities and using data analytics. The findings also showed that lecturers had low degree of proficiency in producing engaging online courses, using adaptive e-learning resources and assistive technologies, and leading group online projects, but have some e-learning skills in providing inclusive education services through communication tools like email, video chat, and text messages. The lecturers faced numerous challenges in integrating e-learning skills for inclusive education service delivery, such as lack of inadequate assistive technologies, high cost of internet broadband, unsatisfactory student-computer ratio, and inadequate e-learning facilities. Based on that suggestions were made.

Key Words: Competency Needs; Inclusive Education Service; Special Education Lecturers and e-learning Skills

Introduction

Teaching in special education provides students with diverse learning needs such as the knowledge, skills, and competencies to develop independence and participate actively in their communities (Ferriman, 2019). Special education teaching involves imparting functional life skills, adaptive behaviours, social interaction, communication, and specialized curriculum to meet the unique needs of individuals with disabilities. The integration of technology has transformed education, enabling special educators to transcend traditional classroom boundaries (Ferriman, 2019). In Nigeria, special educators need to possess competencies that create accessibility to inclusive education services for students with disabilities, as inclusive education aims to educate students with disabilities alongside mainstreamed students (Umar & Abdullah, 2020). Inclusive service delivery must consider students with special needs to achieve the goal of inclusion, including accessibility, personalization, equity, collaboration, and empowerment.

Competencies connote professional understanding, teaching methods, motivational, material utilization, evaluation, adaptive training and support system (Umar & Abdullah, 2020). Special education lecturers must fulfill a capacity to plan, regulate and promote communication in the classroom for effective school integration. The provision of inclusive knowledge is essential to enable lecturers play an efficient part in inclusive service delivery. Successful inclusive education service delivery relies on the competency of lecturers in e-learning skills. e-learning includes the usage of computer technology as a means of running regular academic activities and it is fast gaining recognition nearly in every society (Olowonisi, 2016). Ibezim (2013) earlier stated that e-learning has in essence become one of such tools that is being frequently used to enhance teaching and learning in the 21st century. In effect, today, the scope of e-learning has been expanded to encompass all activities of electronically-mediated teaching (Kyari, Adiuku-Brown, Abechi & Adalokun, 2018), with the potential to impart learning in a much more efficient and interactive manner. With the use of e-learning skills becoming increasingly popular in the educational arena, there is further need for competency among lecturers to ensure that learners in inclusive settings are supported.

Special education lecturers are trained professionals who specialize in teaching students with disabilities or special needs. Their goal is to create an inclusive learning environment that caters to the diverse needs of their students. According to Rashid, et al., (2009), special education lecturers need to possess a range of digital competencies to deliver inclusive learning experiences using e-learning skills. They must demonstrate digital literacy, technology competence, and the ability to create and curate engaging digital learning materials (Nwagwu & Azil, 2016). Additionally, they need to be able to design adaptive and personalized e-learning experiences and facilitate both synchronous and asynchronous online learning activities. However, the integration of technology for

teaching and learning has been slow in Africa (HafizuIsmail & Adamu, 2017). Researchers have investigated the possible causes of this slow adoption, including the need to assess the competency needs of special education lecturers in using e-digital technology for service delivery (Engin, 2017). Based on these, the present study aimed to investigate the essential competency needs of special education lecturers in Federal College of Education, Pankshin, to effectively utilize e-learning skills for inclusive education service delivery.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the benefits of technology in enhancing education, some special education lecturers in Nigerian higher institutions are hesitant to adopt technology to improve inclusive service delivery. This resistance raises questions about the factors contributing to this reluctance, including pedagogical training, digital literacy, and institutional support. In FCE Pankshin, many lecturers prefer traditional face-to-face teaching methods over e-learning, despite its potential for inclusive service delivery. This is due to a lack of competence and experience in using e-learning skills. Special education lecturers, in particular, lack adequate e-learning skills for technological integration, which hinders effective service delivery. The under-utilization of technological gadgets provided by the government is attributed to lecturers' non-challant attitudes towards adopting e-learning skills. This prompted the researchers to investigate the competency needs of special education lecturers in using e-learning platforms for inclusive education service delivery in Federal College of Education, Pankshin.

Objectives

The objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the competency needs of special education lecturers in utilizing e-learning platforms for inclusive education in Federal College of Education, Pankshin.
2. Identify the e-learning skills for enhancing inclusive education service delivery by special education lecturers in Federal College of Education, Pankshin.
3. Ascertain the challenges faced by special education lecturers in incorporating e-learning skills for inclusive education service delivery in Federal College of Education, Pankshin.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study: -

1. What is the competency needs of special education lecturers in utilizing e-learning skills for inclusive education services in Federal College of Education, Pankshin?
2. What is the extent of e-learning skills for delivery of inclusive education services by special education lecturers in Federal College of Education, Pankshin?

3. What challenges do special education lecturers encounter when integrating e-learning skills for inclusive education service delivery in Federal College of Education, Pankshin?

Hypothesis

A null hypothesis was postulated to guide the study:

There is no significant relationship between the level of lecturers' competency in utilizing e-learning skills and effectiveness of inclusive education service delivery.

Method

Design

The study employed a cross-sectional survey design. The study was conducted in the Department of Special Education, Federal College of Education, Pankshin, Plateau State, North- Central Nigeria. The population of the study was fifteen (15) special education lecturers., the entire 15 Special Education lecturers (7 males and 8 females) were adopted as a purposive sample for the study. A questionnaire entitled "Competency Needs of Special Education Lecturers in Utilization of e-Learning for Inclusive Education Service Delivery (CNSELUEIESDQ)" was used for data collection.

Cronbach Alpha was used to measure consistency or reliability of the instrument. The instrument had a reliability coefficient of 0.82. Hence the instrument was considered suitable for the study. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics The data were displayed using frequency tables, mean and standard deviation (SD) for answering research questions. The research hypothesis was tested using Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis

Research Question 1: What is the competency needs of special education lecturers in utilizing e-learning skills for inclusive education services in Federal College of Education, Pankshin?

Competency needs of Special Education Lecturers in Utilization of E-learning Platforms for Inclusive Education Service in Federal College of Education, Pankshin

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of Competency Needs of Special Education Lecturers in Utilizing E-learning Skills for Inclusive Education Services

S/N	Items	HC	C	SC	NC	\bar{X}	SD
1	Ability to design and develop interactive e-learning content.	7	3	5		3.13	.915
2	Proficiency in using assistive technologies.	2	8	3	2	2.67	.90
3	Competence in creating and facilitating collaborative e-learning activities.	1	-	8	6	1.73	.79
4	Ability to utilize data analytics to monitor student progress.	2	3	1	9	1.87	1.187
5	Knowledge of e-Learning Platforms	8	4	-	3	3.13	1.187
6	Ability to address technological challenges for service deliver in inclusive education.	2	3	2	8	1.93	1.163

Key:

Highly Competent (HC)

Competent (C)

Somewhat Competent (SC)

Not Competent (NC)

Table 1 reveals the mean and standard deviation responses on competency needs of special education lecturers in utilizing e-learning platforms for inclusive education services. The table shows that items 1, 2 and 5 with the mean scores and standard deviations of (\bar{X} =3.13=SD.914; \bar{X} =2.67=SD.90 and \bar{X} =3.13=SD1.187) which were above the criterion mean score of 2.50 were accepted whereas, items 3, 4 and 6 with the mean scores and standard deviation of (\bar{X} =1.73=SD.79; \bar{X} =1.87=SD1.187 and \bar{X} =1.93=SD1.163) less than the criterion mean score therefore, they are rejected. This implies that special education lecturers in FCE Pankshin demonstrated a moderate level of competency in designing interactive e-learning content and knowledge of e-learning platforms and use of assistive technologies but with low level of competency in the creation of collaborative e-learning activities data analytics to monitor student progress and addressing technological challenges in inclusive education settings.

Research Question 2: Which is the e-learning skills for delivery of inclusive education services by special education lecturers in Federal College of Education, Pankshin?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of E-learning Skills for Delivery of Inclusive Education Services by Special Education Lecturers

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD
1	I have the skills to create interactive and accessible e-learning content.	7	46.7	5	-	3.13	.915
2	I am proficient in utilizing assistive technologies and adaptive e-learning tools.	1	3	5	6	1.93	.961
3	I have the competence to facilitate collaborative e-learning activities that promote inclusive participation.	3	2	4	6	2.13	1.187
4	I have adequate technological literacy skills	1	1	8	5	1.87	.834
5	I can provide inclusive education services through communication tools (e.g., email, video chat, text messages, etc.).	4	7	2	2	2.87	.990
6	I have the skills to provide effective online feedback to support the learning needs of diverse students.	5	5	2	3	2.80	1.146

Key:

Strongly Agree (SA)

Agree (A)

Disagree (D)

Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2 presents data on e-learning skills for delivery of inclusive education services by special education lecturers in FCE, Pankshin. The table shows that items 1, 5 and 6 with mean scores and standard deviation of (\bar{X} =3.13=SD0.915; \bar{X} =2.87=SD0.990 and \bar{X} =2.80=1.146) which were above the criterion mean of 2.50 while items 2, 3 and 4 with the mean scores and standard deviation of (\bar{X} =1.93=SD.961; \bar{X} =2.3=SD1.1187 and \bar{X} =1.87=.834). This signifies that the special education lecturers have some e-learning

skills such as creating interactive/accessing e-learning content, providing information through email, video, chat and text messages and provide online feedback and need to improve in collaborative e-learning activities, adequate utilization of e-learning skills and technological literacy skills.

Research Question 3: What challenges do special education lecturers encounter when integrating e-learning skills for inclusive education service delivery in Federal College of Education, Pankshin?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses of Challenges Special Education Lecturers Encounter when Integrating E-learning Skills for Inclusive Education Service Delivery

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD
1	I don't have professional development opportunities to develop e-learning competencies.	5	7	2	1	3.07	.884
2	My department have limited assistive technologies for inclusive education service delivery.	6	5	-	4	2.87	1.246
3	Irregular power supply in my department affected my e-learning skills.	2	4	6	3	2.33	.990
4	The high cost of Internet broadband.	7	4	1	3	3.00	1.195
5	Unsatisfactory student-computer ratio.	6	6	2	1	3.13	.915
6	Inadequate e-learning facilities.	5	6	-	4	2.80	1.207

Table 3 shows the challenges special education lecturers encounter when integrating e-learning skills for inclusive education service delivery. Items 1, 2, 4, 5 and 6 with their various mean scores and standard deviation of (\bar{X} =3.07=SD.884; \bar{X} =2.87=SD1.246; \bar{X} =3.00=SD1.195; \bar{X} =3.13=SD.915 and \bar{X} =2.80=SD1.207) were greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. However, it was only item 3 with the mean score and standard deviation of (\bar{X} =2.33=SD.990) below the criterion mean was rejected by the respondents.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the lecturers' level of competency in utilizing e-learning skills and effectiveness of inclusive education service delivery

Table 4: Pearson Correlation on Relationship Between Lecturers' Level of Competency in Utilizing E-learning Platforms and Effectiveness of Inclusive Education Service Delivery

		LCe	IES
Level of competency on e-learning (LCe)	Pearson Correlation	1	.161
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.02
	N	8	7
Effectiveness of inclusive education service delivery (IES)	Pearson Correlation	.161	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.02	
	N	8	7

Table 4 shows the significance level, denoted as "Sig. (2-tailed)," as 0.02, which means that the correlation is significant at the 0.05 level. This means the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the level of competency in utilizing e-learning skills and effectiveness of inclusive education service delivery in Federal College of Education, Pankshin.

Discussion

The first research objective showed that lecturers in special education thought of themselves as "Highly competent" when it came to creating interactive online courses. Interactive online competency is the ability of a lecturer to effectively facilitate learning by conveying clear information and possessing proficiency in using digital tools and platforms for adequate instructional delivery. The respondents also believed that, with a moderate degree of skill variation, they were "competent" at using assistive technologies. The study also revealed that the lecturers thought of themselves as "competent" when it came to their understanding of e-learning platforms, which are essential for inclusive education to be successful in the digital age. Based on the finding, lecturers have been assigning homework to students, who then turn it in via email or WhatsApp. To promote inclusive learning settings, the lecturers' ability to design and lead cooperative online learning activities was lacking. They could only be described as "somewhat competent" when it came to using data analytics to effectively track student achievement and make decisions that will promote inclusive education. The survey also showed that the lecturers' proficiency in handling technological difficulties related to service delivery was poor. This means that lecturers had limited skills in addressing technological problems that interfered with their service delivery. For example, if one of the department's

wheelchairs goes down, it will be put on the back burner since nobody knows how to fix it. The findings of Oluseyi, et al., (2020) revealed that while lecturers have some competencies in planning and classroom instruction, they lack sufficient skills in ICT which is crucial for effective teaching in today's digital environment. This is why the study of Jimoh, et al., (2018) revealed that lecturers of vocational electrical/electronic technology in Colleges of Education, Polytechnics and Universities need capacity building for effective operation of computer for teaching, uploading text on internet and using teleconferencing for effective e-teaching. This finding entails that lecturers lack the skills and are interested and ready to receive training on e-teaching and utilizing e-teaching for service delivery in their institution. The College only need to provide e-learning facilities that can provide the competency to break the barriers to service delivery to all students.

Findings also showed that lecturers in special education had a mediocre degree of proficiency when it came to producing engaging and easily navigable online courses. They had trouble using adaptive e-learning resources and assistive technologies. These tools include Learning Management Systems (LMS), Text-to-speech software that reads aloud digital content for students with visual impairments, Speech-to-text software, Augmentative and alternative communication (AAC). Unfortunately, the study area had none of the mentioned tools therefore, they cannot have any skill for service delivery. Furthermore, the instructors demonstrated a passable degree of proficiency in leading group online projects that encouraged involvement from all participants. However, their limited technological literacy made it difficult for them to use technology in a way that would help students learn. In terms of providing inclusive education services through communication tools such as email, video chat, and text messages, the lecturers had some level of skill. This is why the findings revealed that the lecturers communicate and provide online feedback such as responding to students' assignments and questions on Departmental WhatsApp group to support the learning needs of diverse students. This has enabled all students to have access to academic information and could participate in the learning process. The findings of Chia (2022) indicated that WhatsApp facilitates flexible communication and learning for students including those with hearing impairment, some teachers resist using the application due to time constraints and a preference for communicating school activities to the students physically or on paper. Teachers need to have the application in their Android phone in order to exchange information with the students with hearing impairment. On the other hand, the findings of Umar, et al., (2021) supported that an excessive number of tertiary students prefer to use WhatsApp for learning purposes therefore, lecturers must possess this skill in order to meet up their learning needs.

The study revealed the challenges faced by special education lecturers in developing their e-learning competencies. Firstly, the respondents reported a lack of

professional development opportunities to enhance their e-learning skills, which was disputed by the researchers who noted that many lecturers had received training in their areas of specialization. However, the study suggested that further training in e-learning skills is still necessary to deliver quality inclusive education services. Additionally, the study revealed that the Department of Special Education in FCE, Pankshin lacked adequate assistive technologies, which are essential for inclusive education service delivery. This needs calls for the College to invest in these technologies to support lecturers in delivering inclusive education services to all students. Furthermore, the study identified several other challenges faced by lecturers, including the high cost of internet broadband, an unsatisfactory student-computer ratio, and inadequate e-learning facilities. Many respondents did not have personal laptops or computers for students, and only a few were computer literate. The College's effort to provide internet connection for each department was hindered by a non-functional network, making it difficult for computer literate lecturers to integrate e-learning skills into their teaching practices.

The above finding is in line with the study of Thomas and Amaechi (2021) who observed that teachers often fail to build on technology's instructional potentials due to barriers such as institutional and administrative support, training and experience, attitudinal or personality factors and resources. In the same vein, the findings of Tarus, et al., (2015) disagreed with this study as it identified the factors hindering the effective adoption of e-learning technologies in tertiary institutions to include among others: inadequate ICTs and e-learning infrastructure; individual characteristics such as the lack of interest and commitment amongst the teaching staff to use e-learning in instructional delivery. However, this study is in contradiction with the findings of Ajayi, et al., (2009) which revealed that irregular power supply is the most challenge in using e-learning technologies. The present findings agreed with Ajayi, et al. (2009) that, inadequate computer literate teachers and high cost of purchasing computers in schools are additional challenges to support full delivery of services.

Conclusion

The study revealed that special education lecturers in Federal College of Education, Pankshin, have varying levels of e-learning competency, but struggled with adaptive resources, assistive technologies, and data analytics. Challenges included limited professional development opportunities, high internet broadband costs, unsatisfactory student-computer ratios, and inadequate e-learning facilities. To improve inclusive education service delivery, the College should invest in assistive technologies and develop lecturers' e-learning skills.

Recommendations

1. The College Management should collaborate with the Department of Special Education to provide opportunities for lecturers to acquire e-learning skills for appropriate service delivery.
2. The College should invest in assistive technologies and provide adequate e-learning facilities, including computers and internet connectivity to support lecturers in delivering inclusive education services to all students.
3. Parents should purchase mini laptops and android phones for their wards to have access to academic information and participate in the learning process.

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